

ПЕДАГОГІЧНА АКАДЕМІЯ:
НАУКОВІ ЗАПИСКИ

ТЕОРІЯ І МЕТОДИКА ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ ОСВІТИ

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Hard skills as a key factor in the future professional success of students majoring in “Library, information and archival studies”

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Abstract. *Purpose:* This study investigates the development of hard skills among students majoring in "Library, Information, and Archival Studies" to identify essential technical competencies and propose strategies for incorporating these skills into the educational process. The research focuses on cataloging, metadata management, digital resource preservation, and information security as key elements in shaping competent professionals for the evolving information society. *Methods:* The analysis synthesizes insights from scientific literature on hard skills development, emphasizing their integration into traditional and distance learning. Methodological approaches include theoretical exploration, practical applications through internships and simulations, and the adoption of online courses and case studies to ensure alignment with modern professional demands. *Results:* The findings reveal that mastering hard skills, such as cataloging, database management,

digitization, metadata usage, and analytical tools, is integral to professional success. Effective training incorporates theoretical knowledge, practical application, and modern technologies, ensuring readiness for contemporary challenges in library and archival environments. Practical internships and online educational platforms further enhance students' technical expertise and adaptability. **Conclusions:** The systematic development of hard skills is a cornerstone in preparing specialists who can manage, secure, and optimize information resources. By integrating cutting-edge methodologies and technologies into the curriculum, future professionals will meet the demands of a rapidly evolving information landscape, ensuring sustainable contributions to their field.

Keywords: information security, metadata management, digitization, cataloging, database systems, analytical tools, professional training, digital preservation.

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***Анотація. Мета:** Це дослідження досліджує розвиток професійних навичок у студентів спеціальності «Бібліотечна, інформаційна та архівна справа», щоб визначити основні технічні компетенції та запропонувати стратегії для включення цих навичок у навчальний процес. Дослідження фокусується на каталогізації, управлінні метаданими, збереженні цифрових*

ПЕДАГОГІЧНА АКАДЕМІЯ: НАУКОВІ ЗАПИСКИ

ресурсів та інформаційній безпеці як ключових елементах у формуванні компетентних фахівців для інформаційного суспільства, що розвивається.

Методи: Аналіз синтезує уявлення з наукової літератури про розвиток навичок, наголошуючи на їх інтеграції в традиційне та дистанційне навчання.

Методологічні підходи включають теоретичне дослідження, практичне застосування через стажування та симуляції, а також впровадження онлайн-курсів і тематичних досліджень для забезпечення відповідності сучасним професійним вимогам.

Результати: Результати дослідження показують, що оволодіння практичними навичками, такими як каталогізація, управління базами даних, оцифрування, використання метаданих та аналітичних інструментів, є невід'ємною складовою професійного успіху. Ефективне навчання поєднує теоретичні знання, практичне застосування та сучасні технології, забезпечуючи готовність до сучасних викликів у бібліотечному та архівному середовищі. Практичні стажування та освітні онлайн-платформи ще більше підвищують технічну компетентність та адаптивність студентів.

Висновки: Систематичний розвиток професійних навичок є наріжним каменем у підготовці фахівців, здатних управляти, захищати та оптимізувати інформаційні ресурси. Інтеграція передових методологій і технологій у навчальну програму дозволить майбутнім фахівцям відповідати вимогам інформаційного ландшафту, що швидко розвивається, забезпечуючи сталий внесок у свою галузь.

Ключові слова: інформаційна безпека, управління метаданими, оцифрування, каталогізація, системи баз даних, аналітичні інструменти, професійна підготовка, цифрове збереження.

Problem statement. In today's information society, which is rapidly evolving due to advancements in the latest technologies and innovations, library, information

and archival professionals play a key role in the preservation, organization, and dissemination of knowledge. However, to successfully fulfill their professional tasks, these specialists need not only general professional competencies but also active development of hard skills — specific technical and specialized skills that enable them to work effectively with information systems, technology, and management processes.

Literature review. The formation and significance of hard skills are widely studied in both foreign and domestic scientific literature. The studies by Pogosov Ye.[11], Savchenko O. [14], Lesovets N. [9], Voronova O. [18], Kazachiner O. [7], Shlenova M. [15], Samoliuk N. [13] focus on the study of hard skills development among higher education students across various contexts. The authors analyze the characteristics of developing technical and professional skills in both traditional and distance learning environments, emphasizing the adaptation of educational programs, the use of digital technologies, and the unique aspects of training specialists in the fields of information and documentary studies, foreign language teaching, and inclusive education. The papers highlight the importance of integrating hard skills with general competencies to enhance the professional effectiveness of future specialists. The works by Heckman J. [5], Hendarman A. [6], Zhang A. [19], Lamri J. [8], Dennis R. [2] explore the development, assessment, and integration of hard skills within educational and professional contexts. They examine the relationship between hard and soft skills, their impact on innovation, training transfer, and employability, and propose frameworks for their unified development. The studies highlight the importance of technical expertise while emphasizing the need to complement it with interpersonal and adaptive skills for holistic professional growth.

Unresolved Aspects and Areas Requiring Further Research. The article highlights the importance of developing hard skills for professionals in "Library, Information, and Archival Studies" but leaves certain aspects unresolved. The

interplay between hard and soft skills, the long-term effectiveness of training strategies, and adapting to rapidly evolving technologies require further exploration. Challenges in distance learning, tailoring skills for niche subfields, and cross-cultural differences in skill development also merit deeper investigation. The author contributes by proposing a robust framework that integrates practical training, technological tools, and modern methodologies. Emphasizing internships, case studies, and online platforms, the work bridges theory and practice, offering innovative approaches to professional preparation in this field.

The purpose of the article is to examine the process of developing hard skills in future specialists majoring in “Library, information and archival studies”, to identify the core competencies essential for their professional activities, and to propose strategies for developing these skills within the learning process.

Research methods. The article employs a variety of scientific methods, both theoretical and practical, to investigate the development of hard skills among students majoring in "Library, Information, and Archival Studies." Below is a description of these methods: The *literature review* analyzes works by domestic and foreign scholars to identify trends, challenges, and best practices in developing hard skills within professional education. *Comparative analysis* is used to compare methodologies and practices for hard skills development across traditional and distance learning environments. This includes assessing the effectiveness of digital tools, online platforms, and face-to-face practical training. *Theoretical modeling* employs conceptual frameworks to define the relationship between hard skills and other competencies. This method outlines the structure and content of professional training programs that support holistic competency development. The research reviews the content of educational programs, online courses, and professional training platforms to identify their contribution to developing hard skills. Each of these methods contributes to the overarching aim of understanding and enhancing the

process of hard skills development for library, information, and archival professionals.

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the scientific results obtained. Hard skills are technical and practical skills that can be measured, tested, and developed through training and experience. For library, information and archival professionals, the main hard skills include knowledge of cataloging, working with information systems, archiving, digitization, database management, and proficiency in software tools for working with information resources and document management.

Mastering hard skills is an important stage of professional training, which Tanko T. [16] conceptualizes as a set of organizational and pedagogical measures aimed at forming a system of knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for ensuring professional readiness in the subject of professional orientation. The acquisition of hard skills, such as technical and specialized skills, is an important part of this process, as they allow one to perform specific tasks and achieve a high level of professional efficiency. In combination with motivation, knowledge, and cognitive aspects, hard skills form the basis for effective professional performance, as their acquisition determines the ability of a specialist to perform practical tasks in real life.

Pogosov Ye. [11] highlights approaches to the formation of professional skills (hard skills) in future specialists in higher education institutions. The author analyzes the specifics of curricula, methods, and tools that contribute to the development of technical and specialized skills, and also justifies the importance of integrating these competencies with general soft skills to improve professional efficiency.

Savchenko O. et al. [14] study how distance learning affects the formation of hard skills in higher education students. They focus on the use of digital technologies and online tools that contribute to the development of technical competencies, particularly in fields where practical skills are critical.

Pekhota O. et al. [10] defines professional training as a continuous educational process that includes three key subsystems: theoretical, research, and practical. In the context of mastering hard skills, it is important that this system provides for systematic consistency and coherence in the goals, content, methods, and forms at each stage of the educational process, which is the basis for preparation for continuous professional development. The development of hard skills, in particular technical and specialized skills, combined with research activities, provides an opportunity to adapt to changing conditions of the profession, maintaining a high level of professional efficiency.

It should be noted that professional training should take into account not only the breadth and content of knowledge, but also the dynamic nature of the educational process, which ensures that a specialist is prepared for continuous development and adaptation to new challenges. The integration of theoretical, practical, and research components into professional training allows students to develop a comprehensive competence that contributes to their effective performance in the professional arena.

Lesovets N. [9] explores the importance of hard skills for students studying information and documentation studies. The author analyzes the methods of forming technical and specialized knowledge in the field of information management, the use of databases, and other information technologies.

Tylikina N. & Krymova M. [17] emphasize that the professional competence of specialists in the field of library, information and archival affairs requires the mastery of Hard Skills, which enable effective performance amid rapid changes and advancements in information technologies. These include expertise in modern information systems, proficiency in data management, and the ability to work with electronic archives.

The development of these competencies should integrate general education, professional training, and economic aspects, focusing on fostering creative thinking,

independence, and responsibility. Such an approach facilitates the successful adaptation of students to the evolving information environment and promotes their ongoing professional growth.

Voronova O. & Barchii M. [18] highlight the peculiarities of developing hard skills in students during distance learning. The main attention is paid to the problems of adapting educational programs to the online format and providing conditions for the effective mastery of technical and professional skills through digital platforms.

According to Golovan M. [4], the formation of the professional competence of specialists in library, information, and archival affairs should ensure the integration of general education and professional training while fostering the development of creative thinking and independence. This process involves mastering Hard Skills, including working with information systems, managing information, implementing modern technologies, and communicating with users.

The development of these skills occurs during training and is strengthened through professional adaptation, which is particularly crucial in a rapidly changing information environment. This approach provides the foundation for professional excellence and the capacity to address non-standard tasks effectively.

Kazachiner O. [7] analyzes what hard skills are necessary for foreign language teachers in the context of inclusive education. In particular, the author discusses technical skills related to the adaptation of teaching materials to the needs of students with different abilities and the use of digital tools for interactive teaching.

Hendarman A. & Cantner U. [6] examine the interplay between hard skills and soft skills and their collective impact on individual innovativeness. It highlights how technical expertise (hard skills) contributes to innovation capacity, particularly when complemented by strong interpersonal and adaptive skills.

Zhang A. [19] explores the use of peer assessment to evaluate both hard and soft skills, focusing on the practical implications for educational and professional

development. The study discusses how peer feedback can help learners refine their technical competencies and enhance their ability to perform in team settings.

Lamri J. & Lubart T. [8] propose a unified framework for understanding hard and soft skills, and identifying their interconnected components. They discuss how the acquisition of hard skills, such as technical and domain-specific knowledge, benefits from integrating soft skills, enhancing overall employability and performance.

Dennis R. Laker & Jimmy L. Powell [2] investigates the distinct nature of hard and soft skills and how they influence the effectiveness of training programs. It emphasizes the challenges of transferring hard skills from training environments to real-world applications, underscoring the need for tailored educational strategies.

Results of the study. This section reflects the vision of the abovementioned authors on the formation of hard skills in students majoring in “Library, information and archival studies”. Future professionals in this major will only succeed if they acquire interdisciplinary knowledge and skills in addition to their foundational knowledge. These competencies allow for a comprehensive approach to solving professional problems, effective adaptation to the changing environment of information, library, and archival institutions, forecasting the development of the industry, and acting proactively, anticipating future challenges.

The main hard skills for library, information, and archival professionals are the follows:

1. *Cataloging and classification of information resources.* Cataloging is the foundation of any library or archive. The ability to effectively organize and classify information resources is one of the most important hard skills for future professionals. In this process, specialists use international standards such as the International Standard for Cataloging (ISBD) or Universal Decimal Classification (UDC).

2. *Working with information systems and databases.* Most processes in modern libraries and archives are automated. Future professionals should be competent in working with library and archive management software such as ALEPH, Koha, Ex Libris, DSpace, and others. These systems provide access to electronic catalogs, databases, and automate the processes of searching, recording, and processing documents.

3. *Digitization and preservation of digital resources.* Digitization is an important aspect of the work of modern archivists and librarians. This includes not only creating digital copies of documents but also understanding the processes of preservation, access, and management of digital collections. Digitization helps preserve rare and important documents, expand access to them for a wider audience, and ensure long-term storage of information.

4. *Metadata management.* Metadata plays an important role in ensuring the accessibility and discoverability of information in digital archives and libraries. Future professionals should have the skills to create, manage, and apply metadata in accordance with international standards such as Dublin Core, MARC 21, and EAD (Encoded Archival Description).

5. *Working with digital resources and information security.* Ensuring information security and data protection is critical for professionals working with information systems and digital archives. Knowledge of the principles of information protection, the use of modern technologies to preserve data, and the prevention of unauthorized access are essential hard skills for modern librarians and archivists.

6. *Use of analytical tools and research methods.* Library, information and archival professionals should also be proficient in information analysis and research methods. It is important to teach future professionals to work with different types of data, using specialized software for analyzing information flows, user analytics, and generating information reports.

Methodological approaches to the formation of hard skills in the process of training future specialists in library, information, and archival science are multifaceted and complex, requiring the integration of theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and modern technologies. Practical training plays an important role in the educational process, as it provides students with the opportunity to apply the acquired knowledge in real-world settings. Training sessions, workflow simulations, and laboratory work using modern software systems and databases that meet the current requirements of the profession greatly enhance the level of training.

Internships in libraries and archives are a key element of professional training, as they allow students to integrate theoretical knowledge with practical skills, gain real-world experience, and adapt to specific working conditions. This contributes to the development of competence in the specialized fields that specialists will work in the future and also helps form a professional understanding of information resources and documentary collections management.

One of the important components of the methodological approach is the use of online courses and specialized programs that create additional opportunities for the development of hard skills. Platforms such as Coursera, edX, and programs offered by library associations allow students not only to supplement traditional education but also to access the most up-to-date knowledge and practices that can be applied in their professional activities.

The use of case studies is a distinctive approach that allows students to gain a deeper understanding of how theoretical concepts and knowledge can be effectively applied in professional situations. The analysis of real cases, including archival collection management, digitization of collections, implementation of new information systems, and other key aspects of library and archival studies, contributes to the development of critical thinking and analytical skills. This approach also

accelerates the process of developing technical skills necessary to work in a rapidly changing information environment.

Conclusions. The development of hard skills is an essential element in the training of specialists who must be able to work effectively with information resources, ensure their security and accessibility, and adapt to the new challenges and demands of the modern information environment. The evaluation of these skills, which encompasses the integration of theoretical knowledge, practical activities, and the use of the latest technologies in the educational process, facilitates the preparation of competent specialists. These professionals should be able to meet the requirements of the modern professional environment and contribute to its development. The development of hard skills is an essential element in the training of specialists who must be able to work effectively with information resources, ensure their security and accessibility, and adapt to the new challenges and demands of the modern information environment. The evaluation of these skills, which encompasses the integration of theoretical knowledge, practical activities, and the use of the latest technologies in the educational process, facilitates the preparation of competent specialists. These professionals should be able to meet the requirements of the modern professional environment and contribute to its development.

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